

FATTE ACID COMPASITION OF MICROALGAE LIPIDS.

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***Annotation:** All cells have the ability to synthesize fatty acids and phospholipids as a means of maintaining the continuous integrity of existing membranes, as well as in the synthesis of new membranes. But most of the biosynthesis of fatty acids occurs in hepatocytes and adipocytes. This article discusses these essential fatty acids.*

***Key words:** Chlorella, micrologae, fatty acids, phospholipids, organism, palmitate, lipds*

Introduction. In Uzbekistan, microalgae are used as a protein vitamin supplement in the diet of animals, birds and silkworm caterpillars.

One of the most important components of living organic matter are lipids, which largely determine the structural and functional features and energy potential of both the cell and the organism as a whole.

All cells possess the capacity to synthesize fatty acids and phospholipids as a means to ensure continuous integrity of existing membranes as well as in the synthesis of new membranes. However, the majority of fatty acid biosynthesis occurs in hepatocytes and adipocytes.

Synthesis of triglycerides occurs in most cells but predominantly occurs in intestinal enterocytes for the delivery of dietary fatty acids to the body and hepatocytes of the liver for the delivery of endogenous fatty acids to, primarily, cardiac and skeletal muscle and to adipocytes. Adipocytes can be considered the

major cell types tasked with triglyceride synthesis as these are the primary fatty acid storage cells the body.

The synthesis of fatty acids takes place in the cytosol. The synthesis of triglycerides takes place within the endoplasmic reticulum, ER. The synthesis of phospholipids occurs on the cytoplasmic face of the membranes of the ER.

Methods and recommendations

The acetyl groups that are the products of fatty acid and amino acid oxidation are linked to CoASH. CoASH contains a phosphopantetheine group coupled to AMP. The carrier of acetyl groups (and elongating acyl groups) during fatty acid synthesis is also a phosphopantetheine prosthetic group, however, it is attached to a serine hydroxyl in one of the active sites of the fatty acid synthase (FAS) complex. The carrier portion of the synthetic complex is called acyl carrier protein, ACP. This is somewhat of a misnomer in eukaryotic fatty acid synthesis since the ACP portion of the synthetic complex is simply one of many catalytic domains of a single polypeptide. The acetyl-CoA and malonyl-CoA are transferred to ACP by the action of the malonyl/acetyltransferase activity (also called acetyl-CoA transacylase and malonyl-CoA transacylase). The attachment of these carbon atoms to ACP allows them to enter the fatty acid synthesis cycle.

The synthesis of fatty acids from acetyl-CoA and malonyl-CoA is carried out by fatty acid synthase, FAS. Fatty acid synthase is encoded by the FASN gene. The FASN gene is located on chromosome 17q25.3 and is composed of 43 exons that encode a protein of 2511 amino acids.

The active FAS enzyme exists as a head-to-tail homodimer. All of the reactions of fatty acid synthesis are carried out by the multiple enzymatic activities of FAS. Like fat oxidation, fat synthesis involves four primary enzymatic activities. These are (in order of reaction), β -ketoacyl-ACP synthase (contained in a domain composed of amino acids 2–404), β -ketoacyl-ACP reductase (contained in a domain composed of amino acids 1876–2112), 3-hydroxyacyl-ACP dehydratase

(contained in a domain composed of amino acids 874–1106) and enoyl-CoA reductase (contained in a domain composed of amino acids 1564–1854). The two reduction reactions require NADPH oxidation to NADP⁺. The domain that is required for attachment and transfer of acetyl-CoA and malonyl-CoA (acyltransferase domain) is composed of amino acids 493–810. The phosphopantetheine arm of FAS is attached to a domain composed of amino acids 2111-2179.

The primary fatty acid synthesized by FAS is palmitic acid (palmitate). Palmitate is then released from the enzyme via the thioesterase activity of FAS (contained in a domain composed of amino acids 2242–2488). Once released, palmitate can then undergo separate elongation and/or unsaturation to yield other fatty acid molecules.

The objects of study were *Chlorella vulgaris* pcs 76-15 grown on a modified Tamiya mineral medium. FA methyl esters were analyzed on an Agilent Technologies 6890 N instrument with the a flame ionization detector using a 30 m long capillary column coated with the nonpolar HP-5 phase at temperatures from 60 to 2500 C. Carrier gas-helium 30 ml/min.

Table of Phospholipid Composition of Various Mammalian Membranes (% total phospholipid)

Phospholipid Class	Membrane Type					
	Plasma	Mitochondrial	Nuclear	ER	Golgi	Lysosomal
Phosphatidylserine	4%	1% inner; 1% outer	6%	4%	4%	1%
Phosphatidylethanolamine	21%	38% inner; 34% outer	25%	21%	17%	21%
Phosphatidylcholine	43%	41% inner; 49% outer	52%	57%	4%	42%
Phosphatidylinositol	4%	2% inner; 9% outer	4%	9%	9%	6%

Cardiolipin	0%	16% inner; 5% outer	0%	0%	0%	0%
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1-Pathways of phosphatidylinositol, phosphatidylglycerol, and cardiolipin synthesis.

Phosphatidylinositols are synthesized via a condensation between CDP-activated 1,2-diacylglycerols (CDP-diacylglycerol) and myo-inositol via the actions of CDP-diacylglycerol–inositol 3-phosphatidyltransferase which is a bifunctional enzyme encoded by the CDIPT gene. The CDIPT encoded enzyme can generate CDP-diacylglycerol from phosphatidic acid and CTP, a reaction that is also catalyzed by at least two additional CDP-diacylglycerol synthases encoded by the CDS1 and CDS2 genes. The CDIPT encoded enzyme is also referred to simply as phosphatidylinositol synthase, PIS. Various phosphatidylinositol kinases phosphorylate the hydroxyls on the inositol moiety of phosphatidylinositols generating various polyphosphoinositides such as the important phosphatidylinositol-4,5-bisphosphate, PIP₂. Phosphatidylglycerols are synthesized in a two-step process that begins with CDP-diacylglycerol and glycerol-3-phosphate followed by removal of phosphate. Both reactions are catalyzed by phosphatidylglycerophosphate synthase 1 which is encoded by the PGS1

gene. Phosphatidylglycerols and CDP-diacylglycerols are combined through the actions of cardiolipin synthase 1 to form diphosphatidylglycerols (DPG) which are more commonly called cardiolipins. Cardiolipin synthase 1 is encoded by the CRLS1 gene.

Summary.

Moisture, air dry object:13,9%,sum of total lipids isolated from chloroform:methanol:4,0%,sum of total lipids separated by column chromatography on silica gel into lipid groups. The result was,% of their mass: neutral lipids - 27,0%,glycolipids + chlorophyll pigments-56,5%, phospholipids-16,5%.Thin layer chromatography on silufol and silica gel revealed:

In glycolipids: monogalactosyl and digalactosyl diglycerides, sterol glycosides and their esters.

In phospholipids: phosphatidylinositol, phosphatidylethanolamine. The fatty acid composition of each lipid group was analyzed by gas liquid chromatography in the form of methyl esters.

As a result, the studied algae were significantly enriched in palmitic (16:0),oleic(18:1)and linoleic(18:2)acids. The amount of unsaturated fatty acids slightly exceeds the amount of saturated ones. The obtained results indicate that the studied algae include biologically active substances: esters of cyclic alcohols with high molecular weight fatty acids and with acetic acid, sterols, triterpenols and essential fatty acids.

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